

STUDY OF THE BALLET BY P.I. TCHAIKOVSKY "SLEEPING BEAUTY" IN THE THIRD GRADE OF A COMPREHENSIVE SCHOOL

Trigulova A.Kh.

Associate Professor of the Department of Theory and Methods of Teaching Music, TSPU named after Nizami, PhD in Pedagogical Sciences.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15533551>

It is difficult to imagine a more festive spectacle, music more sunny and cheerful than the ballet "Sleeping Beauty" by P. I. Tchaikovsky.

The richness of rhythms, the inexpressible charm of melodies, the colorful instrumentation make "Sleeping Beauty" not only in Tchaikovsky's work, but in all ballet music a remarkable phenomenon.

The idea of the ballet is the victory of light over darkness, happiness over suffering. "Sleeping Beauty" is one of the brightest, life-affirming works of Tchaikovsky. The music is full of festive joy, bright sunshine, and at the same time heartfelt, full-blooded light lyricism, revealing the beauty of the spiritual world of man. The fantastic plot did not become an obstacle for Tchaikovsky to express truthful, truly human feelings. The experiences of Aurora, Desiree, the Lilac Fairy - all these are the feelings of living, sincerely loving and passionately striving for happiness people. But everything human and bright in the ballet is sharply contrasted with another world - the world of malice and hatred, embodied in the ballet also very brightly and vividly in the image of the evil Carabosse. The main conflict between the light and dark forces is embodied in the clash of the two leading musical themes of the ballet: the Lilac theme and the Carabosse theme. Good and humanity defeat evil and violence. Life and joy triumph in music.

In music class, after getting acquainted with the plot of the ballet, we suggest listening to the Themes of the Lilac Fairy and the Carabosse Fairy. Introduction.

Before listening to the fragments of the introduction, you can use the technology of modeling the creative process. Divide the class into creative groups headed by the "Responsible Composer" and ask the students to "compose" the theme - the melody of the Good Fairy and the Evil Fairy themselves, defining the image, character and the main means of musical expression available to third-graders. Hand out the corresponding cards: the nature of the melody's movement - smooth, melodious, jumpy, sharp, intonations - good, evil, song, dance, march, genre features (waltz, march, fantastic dance), mode - dark, light color, register - the pitch of the melody - low, high, medium, tempo - fast, slow, moderate, size, dynamics - loud, quiet,

moderate, crescendo, diminuendo. When the children have completed the task, choose the most successful option. Then listen to fragments of the themes of the Lilac Fairy and the Carabosse Fairy in the introduction, let the children themselves determine where which theme is and compare it with their options. Orchestral introduction. The ballet begins with an orchestral introduction built on two main musical images. Discontinuous ominous chords, sharp intonations of the melody, angular rhythm characterize the theme of the fairy Carabosse. It is displaced by the gentle, smooth melody of the Lilac fairy, all as if woven from rays of light and filled with floral aromas. Beginning barely audible, as if from afar, it sounds stronger and stronger as a jubilant hymn of joy. In it, for the first time, two main musical images collide: the fairy Carabosse and the Lilac fairy.

The characteristics of these two characters, personifying the ideas of evil and good, are sharply contrasting. The composer characterizes Carabosse with a sharp, angular in rhythm, harmonically unstable theme. The theme of the Lilac Fairy, on the contrary, is vocal and melodic by its very nature. In harmonic terms, it is clear, tonally stable (its key is E major, always associated in Tchaikovsky's music with bright lyrical images). The orchestration of both themes is also sharply different. The theme of Carabosse is presented by the entire orchestra. The appearance of the theme of the Lilac Fairy is preceded by a splash of harps, after which a friendly, gentle melody sounds from the flutes and English horn against the background of a soft tremolo of violins and violas pianissimo. The Lilac theme undergoes extensive development in the introduction thanks to the gradual inclusion of melodic subvoice, which fills it with a wide, full-blooded melodic breath. As a result of the great emotional build-up on the tonic quart-sixth chord of E major, a joyful fanfare signal is heard in the fortissimo sound of the wooden instruments and trumpets, as if signifying the victory of the light forces over the forces of darkness.

Further, of great interest to schoolchildren is the "Waltz" in B-flat major from the first act of the ballet "Sleeping Beauty". A bright, festive, jubilant waltz in B-flat major with typical features inherent in the waltz genre. The children themselves will feel the measured swaying of the light melodic line in this famous waltz.

Finale of the first act. Fragments. The theme of the fairy Carabosse sounds in the orchestra, maliciously and triumphantly. This is its new rhythmic and harmonic version: without pauses interrupting the chords, against the background of the tremolo of the organ point B-flat and with new harmonic sequences. The theme of Carabosse then undergoes a great deal of motivic

development. Two of its elements are developed: the progressive movement in seconds and the rhythmic motif in sixteenths, which ultimately, chromatically, becomes the basis of Aurora's dance with a spindle.

Aurora's dance with a spindle. Aurora's dance with a spindle unfolds in a rapid movement (from "Allegro vivo" to "Presto") in the key of C minor. At the end of it, the initial intonations of the Carabosse theme appear, taking on an ominous and tragic character here. Aurora, having pricked herself with a spindle, falls. The cellos and bassoons sound a theme expressing the grief and despair of those around her. The last intonation of this theme - a gradual descending movement - becomes the source of further musical development. The theme of Carabosse in its main form is juxtaposed with this theme of grief and despair (at this point the old woman throws off her cloak and appears as Carabosse. The princes rush at the evil sorceress, but she suddenly disappears). The continuous movement of sixteenth notes in the tempo of "Poco piu vivo", born of the theme of Carabosse and the whirlwind dance of Aurora, ends this dramatic episode of the ballet. It directly leads into the last section of the finale.

The appearance of the Lilac Fairy. Her theme sounds in the English horn in a light E major. At the sign of the good sorceress, the entire kingdom plunges into a magical sleep: a colorful chain of chords sounds in an even rhythmic movement - the "theme of numbness". The entire final scene has a fantastically picturesque character.

In this lesson, you can give a more complete idea of the genre of ballet. Ballet is a musical performance in which the content is conveyed by dance. The dances are accompanied by music. It is performed by a symphony orchestra. The action of the ballet takes place on stage. The entire performance is directed by a conductor. The orchestra, dancers, and ballet soloists obey his baton. Key concepts: ballet, contrast, intonation, images, and their development in music.

References:

1. Нарходжаев Н.Ахмадеева Ф., Утаева Н. «Музыка» Учебник для 3 класса общеобразовательных школ. Т., 2022.
2. Наумов, С. А. Эстетический вкус, его воспитание / С. А. Наумов. - Н. Новгород, 1997. - 135 с.
3. Науменко Т.И., Алеев В.В. Музыка. Учебник для общеобразовательных учебных заведений. 6 класс. – М., 2001 – с. 90
4. Тригулова А.Х. Предметная интеграция и ее значение в профессиональной подготовке будущего учителя музыки. Молодой учёный №12 (198) март 2018 г.- с. 173-175

5. Trigulova, A. X. (2021). Formation Of The Cognitive Activity Of 5-Class Secondary School Students With The Familiarity Of The Instruments Of The Symphony Orchestra. Экономика и социум, (4-1 (83)), 428-431.
6. Trigulova, A. (2024). The significance of bv asafyev's intonation theory in the instrumental-performance training of a music teacher. The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations, 6(09), 192-195.
7. Trigulova, A. X. (2023). Musiqiy faoliyat vositasida talabalarning ma'naviy dunyosini shakllantirish. Science and Education, 4(5), 1208-1211.
8. Trigulova, A. X., & Axunova, U. (2023). For participation in the scientific conference «Innonative research in modern edification» with an article entitled. Stylistic approach in music pedagogy, 20.
9. Umida Axunova., Trigulova, A. X. (2024). Fortepianino o'qituvchilar amaliyotida uslubiy yondashuv. Eurasian Journal of Technology and Innovation, 2(2), 142-144.
10. Trigulova, A. X. (2023). Musiqiy faoliyat vositasida talabalarning ma'naviy dunyosini shakllantirish. Science and Education, 4(5), 1208-1211.